

Principles of Accounting Unit 16

Common Size Ratio Analysis: Beyond the Numbers Case Study

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CASE OUTLINE

Financial ratio analysis is an important skill for business leaders. It can help to benchmark performance within an industry or compare companies across industries.

You should compare ten real companies in different industries using the following data:

- Common size balance sheet (Case Exhibit 1)
- Common size income statement (Case Exhibit 2)
- Selected financial ratios (Case Exhibit 3).

A key to the ratio calculations is included in Case Exhibit 4.

All 5 companies are listed in the UK. Their financial information is typical of their sector. Using the case exhibits, you are asked to identify the industry of companies A to E, from the following:

- Supermarket chain
- Online-only retailer
- Housebuilder
- Airline
- Delivery company (food)

HINT: Review the data carefully for the key characteristics of each industry e.g. balance sheet structures.

SKILLS DEVELOPED

Completing this case develops the following skills:

Knowledge and understanding – understanding of the operational context of different companies and the impact on their financial statements and ratios.

Application skills – application of ratio analysis to real data.

Communication skills – explaining the process used to match the data with the industry.

Exhibit 1

Case Exhibit 1	A	B	C	D	E
Revenues	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Cost of sales	-59%		-93%	-82%	-64%
Gross profit	41%	100%	7%	18%	36%
Operating expenses	-48%	-94%	-6%	-5%	-38%
Operating profit	-7%	6%	2%	13%	-2%
Non-operating items	0%	0%	0%	0%	-1%
Finance income	0%	2%	0%	0%	2%
Finance costs	-1%	-2%	-1%	-1%	0%
Share of results in Associates & JVs	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Profit before tax	-8%	5%	1%	13%	-1%
Income tax expense	2%	-1%	0%	-3%	0%
Profit for the year	-6%	4%	0%	10%	-2%

Exhibit 2

Case Exhibit 2	A	B	C	D	E
Goodwill	1%	4%	3%	11%	0%
Other intangible assets	25%	3%	0%	2%	7%
Property, plant and equipment	14%	49%	37%	1%	4%
Right of use assets (leases)	11%	0%	17%	1%	5%
Deferred tax assets	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Investments, equity, associate, JV	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Trade and other receivables	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%
Amounts due from financial services customers and other banks	0%	0%	6%	0%	0%
Other	1%	2%	6%	2%	0%
Total non-current assets	53%	58%	70%	16%	18%
Current assets					
Inventories	29%	0%	8%	65%	1%
Trade receivables	3%	1%	1%	1%	9%
Other receivables	0%	2%	2%	1%	5%
Amounts due from financial services customers and other banks	0%	0%	12%	0%	0%
Cash and cash equivalents	13%	30%	8%	16%	59%
Other financial assets	1%	2%	0%	0%	7%
Other	0%	7%	0%	0%	0%
Total current assets	47%	42%	30%	84%	82%
Total assets	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Exhibit 2 continued.

Case Exhibit 2	A	B	C	D	E
Current liabilities					
Trade payables	3%	4%	15%	4%	2%
Other payables	23%	14%	5%	10%	30%
Amounts owed to financial services customers and other deposits	0%	0%	22%	0%	0%
Borrowing and overdrafts	0%	4%	0%	0%	0%
Deferred income	0%	15%	0%	0%	0%
Other	1%	5%	3%	4%	7%
Total current liabilities	27%	42%	46%	18%	39%
Non-current liabilities					
Borrowings and other financial liabilities	26%	15%	5%	2%	0%
Other	14%	15%	22%	9%	11%
Total non-current liabilities	40%	30%	27%	12%	11%
Total liabilities	67%	72%	73%	30%	50%
Equity					
Called up share capital	0%	2%	3%	1%	1%
Share premium	12%	22%	6%	3%	0%
Other reserves etc	3%	2%	6%	14%	138%
Retained earnings	18%	2%	13%	52%	-89%
Equity portion of convertible debt	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Equity attributable to parent	33%	28%	27%	70%	50%
Non-controlling interests	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Total equity	33%	28%	27%	70%	50%
Liabilities plus equity	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Exhibit 3

Case Exhibit 3	A	B	C	D	E
Cash ratio	0.13	0.30	0.08	0.16	0.59
Acid test ratio	0.65	1.00	0.49	1.02	2.06
Current ratio	1.73	1.00	0.66	4.62	2.10
Accounts receivable days	8.37	4.91	1.41	4.85	17.14
Inventory turnover	2.72		15.76	0.83	88.08
Inventory days	134.09		23.16	439.86	4.14
Asset turnover	1.35	0.83	1.30	0.66	1.99
Accounts payable days	12.45		45.25	26.06	4.48
Working capital cycle	130.01		-20.68	418.66	16.80
Debt to total assets	26%	15%	5%	2%	0%
Debt to equity	0.77	0.52	0.16	0.04	0.00
Gross margin %	41%	100%	7%	18%	36%
Operating margin	-7.0%	5.5%	1.6%	13.3%	-2.2%
Interest cover	-4.67	2.52	1.58	20.27	-17.48

Exhibit 4 – Key to ratio calculations

Ratio	Calculation
Liquidity	
Cash ratio	Cash/Total assets
Acid test ratio	(Current Assets-Inventory)/Current Liabilities
Current ratio	Current Assets/Current Liabilities
Efficiency	
Accounts receivables days	(Accounts receivable/Revenues)*365
Inventory turnover	Inventory/Revenue
Inventory days	(Inventory/Cost of Sales)*365
Asset turnover	Revenue/ Total Assets
Accounts payable days	(Accounts Payable/Cost of Sales)*365
Working capital cycle	AR + Inventory days – AP days
Financial leverage ratios	
Debt to total assets	Long-term borrowings/total assets
Debt to equity	Long-term borrowings/total equity
Profitability ratios	
Gross margin %	Gross profit/revenue
Operating margin	Operating profit/revenue
Interest cover	Finance costs/operating profit

References

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